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Harnessing Artificial Intelligence in Fascinating and Fecund Teaching and Learning of Christian Religious Studies for Global Evangelization

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Abstract

Christian Religious Studies (CRS) is offered in all Nigerian educational institutions as subjects in basic schools, junior secondary schools and senior secondary schools. Also, it is offered as an academic program in tertiary institutions as Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE), Bachelor in Education (B. Ed.), Masters of Education (M. Ed.) and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph. D). However, it is becoming unattractive to the present generation of students. This era where science and technology increasingly permeate daily life, the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) could be employed in teaching and learning CRS to make it a fascinating and fecund subject. Therefore, "Harnessing Artificial Intelligence in fascinating and fecund Teaching and Learning of Christian Religious Studies for global evangelization" researched into relevance, challenges and prospects of AI to teaching and learning of CRS. Descriptive research approaches were adopted to collate information of this work, which was based mainly on relevant internet and library materials, which were studied and apply appropriately. The findings of the research were discussed with headings such as Artificial Intelligence and Christian Religious Studies, relevance of integrating AI into teaching and learning of CRS and challenges and prospects of AI in teaching and learning of CRS. The paper concluded that the use of AI with continuous supervision and evaluation will enhance fascinating and fecund teaching and learning of CRS thereby improving the interest, inclusiveness and performance of students. This will in turn enhance global evangelization. Finally, the paper recommended among others that, the use of AI in teaching especially CRS in the schools should be encouraged. Also, seminars, workshops and in-service training should be organized for teachers to enable them acquire knowledge and skills about design selection, production and use of AI in schools.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Christian Religious Studies, Fascinating and Fecund, Teaching and Learning

Introduction

Christian Religious Studies (CRS) is offered in all Nigerian educational institutions as subjects in basic schools, junior secondary schools and senior secondary schools. Also, it is offered as an academic program in tertiary institutions as Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE), Bachelor of Education (B. Ed.), Masters of Education (M. Ed.) and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph. D). CRS, which is pivotal to global evangelization, is "reflecting the country's rich religious heritage and occupies a significant place in Nigeria's educational system" (Nicholas Idoko Technologies, 2024). As one of the oldest subjects in in global education, especially in Nigerian schools, CRS aims to inculcate specific values and knowledge in learners (Kesmen & Mellemut, 2022). However, in this modern era, where science and technology increasingly permeate daily life, CRS is becoming unattractive to people, parents and pupils alike. Meanwhile, the importance of modern technologies in disseminating Christian Religious knowledge that will propel evangelistic concern in people via teaching and learning of CRS cannot be over emphasis. Therefore, application of relevant and modern technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) may help to solve some of the identified problems faced in the effective teaching and learning of the subject. For it is an age long belief in educational technology that modern technologies are essential for effective and efficient teaching and learning (Alaba, 2008).

Artificial Intelligence and Christian Religious Studies

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the creation of computer systems capable of performing tasks that historically only a human beings could do, such as reasoning, making decisions, or solving problems. It is also the mechanical stimulation of human intelligence processes especially computer systems. Specific application of AI includes expert systems, natural language processing, speech recognitions, machine visions etc. It is computing systems that are able to engage in human-like processes such as learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correction and the use of data for complex processing tasks (Popenici and Kerr, 2017). According to AFSA (2022), Copeland (2023), Alagbe (2023), and Ogunode & Ukozor (2023), AI encompasses computer systems and technologies that emulate human intelligence, undertaking tasks like learning, reasoning, and problem-solving. These technologies, including machine learning and robotics, have diverse applications across sectors such as health care, finance, transportation, and education, holding the potential to revolutionize industries and create new opportunities for advancement. The multifaceted nature of AI programming, highlighted by Laskowski & Tucci (2023), is characterized by cognitive skills such as learning, reasoning, self-correction, and creativity. Learning involves acquiring data and creating procedures for actionable information, while reasoning focuses on choosing the right process for desired outcomes. AI has quickly established itself as a transformative force in a wide range of industries, including education.

In the words of Firuz, Firuz and Ikhlaas (2023), the development of AI has resulted in an array of advancements and innovations that have impacted many facets of human life. As a fundamental component to societal evolution and individual development, education has had significant benefits from AI breakthroughs. The integration of AI in educational systems is altering the ways in which students learn, teachers educate, and institutions function. By personalizing learning experiences, automating administrative responsibilities, and delivering real-time feedback, AI is revolutionizing the educational landscape, bridging gaps, and encouraging a more inclusive and effective learning environment (Firuz, Firuz and Ikhlaas (2023). AI in education is the application of sophisticated technology, namely machine learning procedures and computational models, to enhance the learning process, boost educational results, and customize instruction to meet the unique requirements of each student (Schueller, Tomasino and Mohr, 2017).

Copeland (2024) underscores that AI refers to the capability of a machine to undertake tasks generally perceived to entail human rationality and intelligence. He stressed that general operations of AI include game playing, language translation, expert systems, and robotics. Copeland enlightens that while the notion of machines imitating intelligence dates back to the ancient past, the advent of authentic intelligence in machines was only possible with the evolution of digital computers in the 1940's. He streamlines that AI has evolved to the point that the initial AI projects via playing chess and solving mathematical problems, are now considered quite plain compared to the more complex tasks of AI in recent times like visual pattern recognition, complex decision making, and the use of natural language. In addition, there are several scholars who described AI from the collective point of view. For instance, Saravanan, Sreedevi and Subhamathi (2017) defined AI as a study of how to make computers perform activities that people cannot do better. Similarly, Haenlein and Kaplan (2019) defined AI as "a system's ability to interpret external data correctly, to learn from such data, and to use those learning to achieve specific goals and tasks through flexible adaptation."

On the hands, Christian Religious Studies (CRS) is the type of education in which the curriculum, teaching and other educational practices are determined by a Christian religious worldview, which holds that there is a Supreme Being who is responsible for the existence of everything, seen and unseen (Miracle, 2015). It aims to shape students' character for successful living and acceptance before God in worship, guiding them toward the attainment of human and Christian ideals. Abolarin and Babalola (2020) claimed that CRS is designed and integrated into the school curriculum; and its teaching is based on a Christian religious

worldview. Alongside the teaching in school, it is taught at home since the home is the first school in a persons' life. Okeke (2021) posits that CRS is part of the holistically oriented education that guides the students toward progressive habits for social responsibilities for the community they belong to. So, this type of education aimed at guiding students to emulate the characters of our Lord Jesus Christ, which includes love, integrity, humility, obedience, gentleness, and the fear of God should be well accepted by Christians. Thus, instill subtle concerns for evangelization in them. Meanwhile, reversed is the case nowadays, most pupils from Christian homes reject CRS at primary and secondary levels, and refused to make it their course of study at tertiary institutions even when they are qualified to offer it. This researcher underscores that employment of AI in teaching and learning CRS will enhance fascinating and fecund result.

The Relevance of Integrating AI into Teaching and Learning of CRS

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Christian Religious Studies (CRS) holds great potential to transform the way religious teaching and learning is conducted. Since the origin of the establishment of education, the strategies of teaching and also the bond shared between learners and educators have evolved considerably. Teaching strategies across the world became additional structured to administer higher, and to achieve efficient results. This transformation is majorly attributed to the continued intervention of technology. Educational stakeholders are actively looking for ways to smoothly integrate AI into curriculum at all levels of education for fascinating and fecund teaching and learning given the necessity of AI in this constantly changing world. The potential for AI to revolutionize traditional teaching and learning methodologies is underscored by its capacity to provide personalized and adaptive approaches.

By analyzing individual data, AI can provide personalized and profound spiritual guidance tailored to the needs and development of each student. In this regard, AI can become a valuable partner for educators and spiritual leaders in guiding students on their spiritual journeys. Secondly, Artificial Intelligence can enhance the understanding of Christian teachings through in-depth analysis of biblical texts. By utilizing natural language processing capabilities, AI can provide contextual and historical insights, enriching students' understanding of the spiritual messages contained therein. Thirdly, the implementation of AI in the development of spiritual applications opens up new possibilities for experiencing Christianity in practical everyday contexts. According to Samuel and Santiana (2023) AI-based applications can provide personalized prayers and meditations, assisting students in practicing spirituality in their daily lives. Buckingham and Ferguson (2016) elaborate on how AI can analyze individual student performance, preferences, and learning styles through machine learning algorithms. This data-driven approach enables the creation of tailored educational experiences, optimizing the learning process for each student's unique needs and abilities. They further emphasize the transformative potential of AI in facilitating a shift from standardized education to personalized learning experiences. By adapting content and pacing to individual progress, AI technologies can enhance engagement and effectiveness in teaching and learning of CRS, thus, fostering a more dynamic and student-centric learning environment (Buckingham and Ferguson 2016).

Chen, Xie, Zou & Hwang (2020) claim that the application of AI is capable to ease the work of the teacher in schools, including teaching automation and evaluation, teacher administration, keeping learner attendance, intelligent teaching systems for special education and recommending useful materials for pupils. Further to that, AI technologies also perform social roles in education. For instance, AI assisted devices enable educators to interact with smart machines in ways that inspire both educator and learners to explore more spaces for enhancing teaching and learning experiences. One of such patterns of learning is the individualized method. Espousing this argument, Pedro, Subosa, Rivas & Valverde (2019) stated that AI powered education supports a reform that aims to create a tutor system that can transform learning to a personalized activity.

Additionally, Kandula (2020) highlighted the relevance of AI in education thus:

AI can automate basic activities in education, like grading: While AI might not ever be ready to actually replace human grading, it's obtaining pretty shut. It's currently potential for academics to alter grading for nearly every kind of multiple alternative and fill-in-the-blank testing and automatic grading of student writing might not be so much behind.

Students could get additional support from AI tutors: These programs will teach students fundamentals. However, up to now AI ideals are not serving to learn high-order thinking and creative thinking, hence, real-world lecturers' square measure still needed to facilitate. Nonetheless, the likelihood of AI tutors having the ability to try to these items within the future should not be ruled out.

AI-driven programs can give students and educators helpful feedback: AI cannot solely facilitate academics and students to craft courses that are tailored to their wants. However, it may give feedback to each concerning the success of the course as an entire. These sorts of AI systems enable students to urge the support they have and for professors to search out areas wherever they'll improve instruction.

It could change the role of teachers: There will always be a job for teachers in education, but what that role is and what it entails may change because of new technology within the type of intelligent computing systems. AI can help students improve learning, and could even be a substitute for real-world tutoring.

Data powered by AI can facilitates differentiation in the classroom: Smart data gathering, powered by intelligent computer systems, is already making changes to how colleges interact with prospective and current students.

Therefore, CRS educators should see Artificial intelligence's personalized capabilities as a reflection of God's design, a tool that acknowledges the uniqueness of each student's talents and gifts. By tailoring content to students' interests and abilities, AI ignites a deeper sense of purpose and meaning in CRS. Instead of mindlessly memorizing historical dates, AI can engage students in exploring historical connections, analyzing cause-and-effect relationships, and considering events from different perspectives. This application fosters critical thinking skills as students seek wisdom and understanding rather than passive acceptance of information.

In addition, AI has ushered in a new age of personalized learning in education. Intelligent tutoring systems can adapt-coursework to most individuals learning capacity and ability; considering their weaknesses and discovering easiest way for enhancing and improving their conception. As well, AI streamlines administrative tasks in education, enabling educators to focus more on effective teaching. In utilizing machine learning algorithms, AI can pin-point at-risk students for timely interventions; ultimately decreasing dropout rates. Moreover, AI-powered content creation tools automate the production of educational materials; enhancing accessibility of quality education which enhances effective and efficient teaching and learning.

Challenges of AI in Teaching and Learning of CRS

While the potential of AI in teaching and learning of CRS is immense, several challenges must be urgently addressed. Many Nigerian schools, particularly rural ones, lack basic digital infrastructure such as internet connectivity, electricity, and computers. The successful implementation of AI will require significant investments in infrastructure. Teachers and students must be digitally literate to benefit from AI-based educational tools. Comprehensive training programs will be necessary to equip CRS educators with the skills needed to AI into their teaching practices. Artificial intelligence's tools and systems are often expensive to implement and maintain. Samuel and Santiana (2023) carefully summarized the challenges of AI in teaching and learning of CRS with the following points:

Training for Teachers: Integrating of AI in teaching and learning of CRS requires a good understanding of technology by teachers. Appropriate training is necessary for teachers to optimize Artificial intelligence's

potential and understand how to integrate it with a holistic approach to CRS. Teachers also need to learn how to manage AI wisely, identify potential weaknesses, and resolve any technical issues that may arise.

Lack of Empathy and Human Experience: While AI may provide information and guidance; it cannot emotionally respond or understand students' personal feelings and challenges in the same way as an educator.

Technology Dependency: Implementing AI in teaching and learning CRS should not result in excessive dependence on technology. While AI can enhance the efficiency of spiritual learning, human educators and spiritual mentors remain irreplaceable. Empathetic human interactions, deep understanding of students and compassionate spiritual guidance have immeasurable value in nurturing students' faith and spiritual development. Educators and religious leaders need to play an active role in directing, guiding, and accompanying students on their spiritual journeys.

Limitations in Understanding Complex Spiritual Dimensions: Spirituality in CRS involves complexities and depths that may not be fully grasped by AI. Deep spiritual experiences encompass elements such as personal beliefs, religious experiences, and unique spiritual growth for each individual. AI may struggle to comprehend these highly personal spiritual dimensions and provide appropriate guidance accurately.

Data Security and Privacy Challenges: The use of AI in CRS involves the collection and analysis of student data, including spiritual activities and spiritual growth. Therefore, safeguarding data of the teacher and student privacy is of utmost importance. Ensuring that teachers and students data is securely stored and used only for spiritual education purposes is a primary responsibility. Establishing clear and transparent privacy policies and complying with relevant data protection regulations will ensure teachers and students' trust and comfort in using AI in the teaching and learning process.

Practical Context: Practically, teaching and learning pose some challenges in the implementation of AI. Not all educational institutions have access to or resources for adopting AI technology, limiting its impact on students in resource-constrained educational environments. While AI offers tremendous potential in enhancing Christian religious learning, addressing these weaknesses is essential to ensure Artificial intelligence's role aligns with Christian values and continues to support human roles in providing empathetic and holistic spiritual support to students.

Prospects of AI in Teaching and Learning of CRS

As we navigate the evolving landscape of education, the integration of AI continues to shape the future of teaching and learning (Alam, 2021). The prospects of AI in teaching and learning of CRS in this 21st century is inevitable in these contemporary times. Therefore, discussed below are some prospects of employing AI in disseminating Christian religious knowledge to learners at various levels of academic pursuit:

Specialized Training for Educators: AI is poised to become a vital resource in teacher training, offering interactive, hands-on workshops designed specifically for CRS educators. These programs could equip teachers with the tech skills they need to blend AI into their classrooms while staying true to Christian values, making it easier to troubleshoot issues and adopt AI confidently in their teaching.

Empathy through AI Assistance: AI cannot replace the supporting empathy of a human teacher. However, it can free up educators by taking over routine tasks. This allows teachers to devote more time to one-on-one interactions, building the compassionate, mentorship-centered relationships that are essential to students' spiritual growth.

Blending Technology and Human Guidance: Artificial intelligence's role in the future can be to handle repetitive tasks, allowing teachers to focus on the spiritual and moral aspects of Christian Religious education. This balance would ensure that technology serves as an aid, not a substitute, reinforcing the human connections that are central to Christian education.

Deeper Discussions with AI Resources: In the future, AI could provide teachers with rich theological resources that support complex discussions. With AI helping to supply scriptural context and historical background, teachers would have more tools to guide students through profound spiritual topics, making lessons more meaningful.

Enhanced Privacy and Ethics in AI Use: Artificial intelligence's capabilities in data protection are expected to advance, which would help address privacy concerns in Christian Religious education. By prioritizing transparent, secure data practices, AI can safeguard students' information and respect their spiritual journeys, building trust and comfort in using technology.

Greater Access for Resource-Limited Areas: AI has the potential to expand Christian religious education into underserved regions by providing affordable, digital access to resources. As AI technology becomes more accessible, CRS educators and institutions could bridge educational gaps, allowing students from all backgrounds to engage in Christian Religious education that will in turn enrich global evangelization.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The integration of AI into the teaching and learning of CRS in all levels of education is capable of enhancing the delivery of lessons, streamlines the preparation of student performance reports, supports the creation of instructional resources, aids in understanding of theological concepts, advances research in Christian religious education, improves the conduct of examinations, and fosters student engagement, motivation, and personalized learning experiences. In addition, the use of AI with continuous supervision and evaluation will enhance fascinating and fecund teaching and learning of CRS thereby improving the level of involvement, participation and performance of students, thus enable them to develop the spirit of evangelism.

Consequently, it is recommended that the use of AI in teaching CRS in the schools and institutions of academic learning should be encouraged. Also, seminars, workshops and in-service training should be organized for teachers to enable them acquire knowledge and skills about design selection, production and use of AI in schools. Likewise, the Nigerian policy on education needs review to produce a framework for the introduction of AI powered education to benefit both private and government owned institutions at all levels. In the same vein, the curriculum of teacher education has to be revised to feature AI in all levels of education. Also, an increased investment in all levels of education, especially the tertiary institutions for the full integration of AI in the full implementation of CRS program in urban and rural schools should be considered. Lastly, continuous professional development for CRS educators to be encouraged and financed by tertiary institutions should be prioritized. This will empower them with the skills to leverage AI tools effectively while safeguarding student well-being.

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